

Temperature-induced microstructure evolution of geopolymer-copper slag composites-implications on high-temperature applications

M. Lassinantti Gualtieri¹, E. Colombini¹, C. Leonelli¹, P. Veronesi¹

¹Department of Engineering “Enzo Ferrari”, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Via P. Vivarelli 10/1, 41125 Modena, Italy

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Presenting author email: magdalena.gualtieri@unimore.it

Introduction

The production of copper is in steady increase due to the growth of global copper demand. Production through pyrometallurgical processing results in a huge amount of slag. A large portion of the copper slag is accumulated in open stockpiles although many different alternative solutions have been developed including recovery of iron and copper (Hau *et al* 2024), as aggregate and binder replacement in cementitious materials (Wang *et al* 2021) and as reactive phase in alkali-activated materials (Adediran *et al* 2023). Another, less noble, application is as grits in blasting operations. Regarding mortars and concrete, the literature is mainly focused on traditional materials performances. An emerging field of interest is cementitious materials where the main task of copper slag aggregate is absorption of electromagnetic waves to mitigate electromagnetic pollution (Guo *et al* 2021; Ma *et al* 2018). Another application of copper slag as microwave absorber was recently explored by Hu *et al* (2022) who found that microwave-aided healing of cracks in asphalt was significantly enhanced by partial replacement of natural aggregates with copper slag. An on-going research project entitled METAWAVE (high-temperature heating processes with breakthrough microwave and digital technologies for increased energy efficiency), financed by the European Union, is aimed at developing novel heating processes utilizing microwave heating. A part of this research is focused on heating element materials. In particular, geopolymer-bonded copper slag are explored. The geopolymer potentially preserves the integrity of the composite material at high temperature (Lahoti *et al* 2019) and copper slag transforms absorbed microwaves to heat. For such materials, the appropriate working temperature is governed by the functional integrity of the material. Hence, this work is aimed at studying the events taking place during heating of geopolymer-copper slag composites. Various *in-situ* methods were used such as optical dilatometry and thermogravimetry in conjunction with differential thermal analyses (TG/DTA). In addition, the temperature-induced microstructural evolution was evaluated through scanning electron microscopy (SEM-EDS) and X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD).

Experimental

Commercial copper slag destined for grit blasting was obtained from Techma (Monte Marengo, Italy). The as-received material had a particle size <1mm. The geopolymer paste was prepared from metakaolin (Argical 1000, Imerys Minerals Ltd., Italy) and alkaline sodium silicate solution: 55.0 wt% metakaolin; 8.8 wt% 8M NaOH-solution; 36.0 wt% sodium silicate solution (46.6wt% solid content; SiO₂/Na₂O molar ratio of 3.0). Composites of as-received copper slag and geopolymer paste were prepared by mixing 32wt% geopolymer paste and 68 wt% copper slag and subsequently cast the resulting concrete in silicon molds. A pure geopolymer sample was also prepared for comparison. Curing was performed at room temperature in a sealed container for at least one month before characterizations. Optical dilatometry was performed using a Misura 3.32 (Expert Solutions, Modena, Italy), applying a heating rate of 10 °/min. TG/DTA measurements were performed using a Netzsch Sta 429 (10°/min in air). A third generation Empyrian instrument from Malvern-Panalytical was used to collect XRPD data whereas a field emission SEM (FESEM - Nova NanoSEM 450 – FEI) equipped with X-EDS Quantax-200 (Bruker) was used for microstructural investigations.

Results and Discussions

According to SEM-EDS, the as-received commercial copper slag contained angular zones (rich in Zn, Al and Cr) in addition to spherical domains (enriched in Cu and Ni) embedded in a chemically homogeneous matrix. XRD data revealed the presence of hercynite (01-089-1692) and fayalite (01-076-0512) in addition to an important background hump indicating the presence of an amorphous phase. The metakaolin contained quartz (00-046-1045), anatase (01-071-1168) and some residual clay minerals (illite 00-043-0685 and kaolinite 00-029-1488) in addition to a background hump representing the reactive amorphous aluminosilicate.

Figure 1 shows the polished cross-section of the hardened composite. Good adherence between copper slag particles and geopolymer matrix is observed (a,b). The geopolymer matrix, as determined by XRD, is *per se* a composite material as the residual crystalline phases present in the metakaolin were preserved following geopolymerization. This was indeed observed in Figure 1c. The large irregular grains with dark contrast clearly observed in (a) were assigned to residual quartz based on EDS point analyses.

Figure 1. Backscattered electron SEM images of the composite at low (a) and high (b) magnification. In (c), a high-magnification image of the geopolymer matrix is shown.

Figure 2. TG/DTA and optical dilatometry results for a pure geopolymer sample (a) and a geopolymer-copper slag composite (b) (TG=blue line; DTA=red line; dilatometry=black line).

Figure 2 shows the results from TG/DTA and optical dilatometry analyses of a pure geopolymer (a) and a geopolymer-copper slag composite (b). Regarding the geopolymer matrix, the first major endothermic event accompanied by weight loss and shrinkage is attributed to water evaporation (Duxon *et al* 2006). The second important event is shrinkage at 915 °C where densification due to viscous sintering starts (Figure 2a). The DTA curve of the composite includes many exothermic crystallization peaks accompanied by oxygen uptake (see Figure 2b). The dilatometry curve shows dimensional stability up to a first contraction at 697 °C, a second one at 908 °C and expansion at 1108 °C. The first contraction is in concomitance to a crystallization peak of copper slag and the second is in concomitance with shrinkage of the geopolymer matrix and a second small exothermic peak in the Cu-slag. The expansion at 1108 °C overlaps with a second broad exothermic peak with a high-temperature shoulder in the DTA curve. The broad peak includes important weight gain (TG) indicating oxidation. The phase evolution with temperature of copper slag has a decisive effect on the dimensional stability of the geopolymer-copper slag composite. This aspect is to be accounted for when designing heating element within this composite system.

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